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DEVELOPMENT OF THE ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE OF THE EMPLOYEE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN AN ACADEMIC LYCEUM

Abstract: This article presents opinions and comments on the development of organizational structures of the personnel management system in educational institutions.

Keywords: management, management, organizational work, structure, employees, organizational structure, order, discipline.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ta'lim muassasalarida xodimlarni boshqarish tizimining tashkiliy tuzilmalarini rivojlantirish bo'yicha fikr va mulohazalar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: boshqaruv, boshqaruv, tashkiliy ish, tuzilma, xodimlar, tashkiliy tuzilma, tartib, intizom.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлены мнения и комментарии по развитию организационных структур системы управления персоналом в образовательных учреждениях.

Ключевые слова: управление, менеджмент, организационная работа, структура, сотрудники, организационная структура, приказ, дисциплина.

Language: English

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Today, the introduction of effective mechanisms for managing the educational process is the most important condition for raising the spiritual, moral and intellectual development of the growing young generation to a new level in terms of quality, as well as innovative forms of education in the educational process. and help to apply the methods. Reforms in the education system aim to create socio-economic, legal, organizational, psychological-pedagogical and other conditions for adapting young people to life, for independent selection and implementation of educational programs. It means raising a mature person who understands his responsibility.

It is very important to use innovative technologies in managing the educational process and improving its quality. Innovative technologies are innovations and changes in the activities of teachers and students in the educational process, and require the use of interactive methods in its implementation. The methods are based on the activity of each student participating in the educational process, free and independent thinking. When using these methods, learning becomes an interesting activity for the student. Innovative technology - methods of improving knowledge acquisition through the use of factors that increase the effectiveness of education, the design and implementation of various pedagogical processes. Its main goal is to introduce innovations and changes in the activities of the teacher and learner in the

educational process, which requires the use of interactive methods. Interactive methods are based on the activity of each learner participating in the educational process, free and independent thinking. When interactive methods are used, students acquire the skills and abilities to work independently with the help and cooperation of teachers. Using these methods, learning becomes a fun activity.

Analysis of literature on the topic; Determining the priorities of the systematic reform of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, raising the process of training highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and high moral and ethical qualities to a new level in terms of quality, modernization of higher education , development of the social sphere and economic sectors based on advanced educational technologies and increasing the effectiveness of scientific and research work in higher education institutions, wide involvement of young people in scientific activities, formation of the innovative infrastructure of science according to the plan of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "O' It was mentioned in the decree No. PF-5847 dated 08.10.2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030".

Innovative technologies in the field of education are constantly developing and their types are expanding. In his time, F.I. Peregudov made a worthy contribution to the field of innovative activity, to the search for

solutions to current problems related to information technologies in education.

Today, as a result of the emergence of a new scientific direction in the field of pedagogy - pedagogical innovation and the idea of renewing the educational process, a new direction in the pedagogical activity of the teacher has also appeared, the concept of "Teacher's innovative activity". Analyzing the concept of "innovative activity", G.A. Mkritichyan's opinion about it is worthy of attention: - "3 main forms of pedagogical experimental activity can be distinguished: private experience, experimental work, innovative activity of the teacher. The more innovations there are in pedagogical activity, the better the teacher understands the private experiment."

The use of new methods in education management is related to the implementation of the ideas of a systematic approach (YU. A. Konarzhevsky, V. S. Lazarev, M. M. Potashnik, P. I. Tretyakov, P. I. Khudominsky, T. I. Shamova, etc.). Systemic approach provides an opportunity to consider the management object as a whole structure consisting of separate but interrelated elements (subsystems) connected to the environment. The components of this system include goals, tasks, structure, technologies. Goals are the generalizing factor that determines the integrity of the system. The systematic approach is based on the use of external and internal mechanisms of management. The main principles of the systematic approach include:

integrity: considering the system as a single integrity and as a subsystem of a higher level;

- Hierarchy (subordination or hierarchy): subordination of lower-level subsystems to higher-level subsystems;

- structuring: analysis of interactions of subsystems within certain organizational structures;

- multidimensionality: the use of different models to describe either individual elements or the entire system (4).

Like any open system, the educational system has inputs, change processes and outputs. Students, personnel, material-technical, educational-methodical, financial conditions and restrictions (regulatory and legal requirements) are understood as input. As a subsystem of education, the process has a complex structure and consists of various sub-processes:

- educational process as a unit of teaching and upbringing;

- educational work and extracurricular activities;

- general educational process;

- teaching by educational levels;

- teaching in classes and parallels;

- teaching in fields of knowledge and special subjects.

The results of educational activities are seen as the output of the educational system. (1) The concept of management by goals is based on the goals agreed upon at different levels of the education system, the ways to achieve them and their evaluation. Based on this concept, the effectiveness of management is determined by the quality of planning and goal orientation. When performing the functions of motivating, managing and organizing the system, the goal becomes the main criterion for choosing the content,

methods, forms and means of implementing the educational process.

There are different approaches to imitating the structure of the teacher's innovative activity. For example, according to A. Nikolskaya, activity renewal is carried out in 3 stages, i.e. preparation, planning and implementation stages.

In higher education, the introduction of innovative technologies, modern methods, analysis and survey methods are used. These documents were studied using systematic and generalization methods, and problems related to the educational process were identified. In addition, scientific proposals and practical recommendations were made using the authors' personal observation and logical thinking methods.

The training of highly qualified and competitive personnel in the higher education system of our country is one of the most important tasks of the system. The effective solution of this task will have a great impact on ensuring the achievement of the goals of socio-economic reforms and the fundamental restructuring of the life of our society. Because the effectiveness of any socio-economic changes directly depends on the professional maturity of the specialists mobilized to perform the tasks set in this regard.

Forms and methods of educational process management in higher education institutions have an incomparable role in social life.

Forms of management of the educational process in higher education institutions in modern conditions are a complex process, the components of which are the correct selection of goals and tasks, the study and in-depth analysis of the achieved level of educational work, rational planning

system, organization of activities of students and pedagogical teams, selection of optimal methods of raising the level of education and training, effective control.

Today, new concepts of management of educational institutions are entering the science of pedagogy, their essence is deeper than the previous ones. For example, instead of the concept of "influence", concepts such as "interaction", "cooperation", "reflexive management" are used.

The purpose of managing the educational system

- Today, new concepts on the management of educational institutions are entering the science of pedagogy, their essence is deeper than the previous ones. For example, instead of the concept of "influence", concepts such as "interaction", "cooperation", "reflexive management" are used, and the theory of management of educational institutions is enriched with the theory of management of educational institutions. Management theory is characterized by trust in employees, creation of conditions for their productive work and mutual respect.

N.A. The concept of dual management of educational quality, developed by Seleznyova, implies the existence of two interacting channels of management: the channel of quality management of system operation (quality assurance) and the channel of quality management of system development (quality improvement). implied by (3). The quality of the system is determined by the quality of all its components: resources, potential (powers), processes (technologies), results. Educational resources are the following: educational support, material-technical and educational-methodical

equipment, personnel, finance. The potential (capacity) of the educational system includes: economic, technological, pedagogical, administrative, educational and other potential

(capacity). Management of the quality of the educational system is focused on ensuring the educational process and forming potentials (powers).

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